

Worku Kebede Tekle
CURRICULUM VITAE

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1. Curriculum vitae

My name is **Worku Kebede Tekle** I am researcher in cereal crop improvement at Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) based on Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center since 2014. I have been working on Tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] improvement program at Ethiopia Institute of Agricultural Research. I received bachelor's degree in plant sciences from Adama Science and Technology University, Ethiopia, and master's degree in plant breeding from Haramaya University, Ethiopia. My MSc thesis topic was "Genetic Variability and Association of Yield and Yield Related Traits in Drought Tolerant Tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] Genotypes".

Since, May 2014 I was a full-time tef breeder in agricultural research and worked closely with national and international collaborators such as the tef improvement project based at the University of Bern in Switzerland. As a breeder I am active member of the research team that has developed a number of technologies appropriate in Ethiopian agriculture and participated in a number of committee teams for crops variety evaluation, crops technology promotion, research system development and etc. I was actively involved in various research activity of crop improvement viz; Agronomic management practices, crop variety development, on-farm performance testing, participatory plant breeding, field and lab data collection, genetic analyses of economic traits using molecular techniques and conventional approach, and multi-location variety trials that led to the development and commercial release of ten tef varieties release and generating scientific information on the crop.

I coordinated the National Tef Research Program for three years (2019 to 2022) at Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research. In the projects titled 1) "Boosting Tef Production and Productivities for Improved Livelihood through Generation and Promotion of Appropriate Technology and Information" and 2) "Integrated Improvement and Food Safety Assessment of Tef in the Face of Climate Change and Emerging Issues," which were funded by the Ethiopian government. During this coordination, with my colleagues I made unreserved efforts and contributions to the tef research program's successes in generating technology and information, as

well as building human and physical capability. Additionally, I am capable of managing projects through program and interpersonal interactions with people from other disciplines, integrate work with different disciplines, and foster a strong sense of teamwork among programs.

I am interested in doing research to advance sophisticated genetic and molecular resources to aid crop improvement, which has a significant economic and social value for smallholder farmers. I am skilled in statistical analysis, SAS, Linux, and R software to some extent, and I am interested to learn more and advance as new technologies become available.

Currently I am PhD student in Agrobiodiversity Program at Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna of Pisa. My research project focusing on Development of pan-genomics and multi-parental mapping tools in tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter].

2. Education

2017 to 2018 MSc. Degree in Plant Breeding: Haramaya University, College of Agriculture, and Department of Plant Sciences Diredawa, Ethiopia. <https://www.haramaya.edu.et>. My thesis topic was "Genetic Variability and Association of Yield and Yield Related Traits in Drought Tolerant Tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] Genotypes". The major findings were estimation of variance components, coefficients of variation, broad sense heritability, correlation coefficients, path coefficient analysis and clustering of the genotype based on variabilities observed. The genetic variability, heritability and, direct and indirect relationships in the tested traits of the genotypes confirmed possibility to improve tef productivity in the target areas through direct selection and hybridization.

2011 to 2013 BSc. Degree in General Agriculture (Plant Science): Adama Science and Technology University, Assela Campus, Ethiopia. <https://www.astu.edu.et>. I studied general agriculture and, more specifically, plant science.

3. Publications

3.1. Articles in journals

22. **Kebede W.** and Assefa K. (2022). Trait association and path analysis in drought-tolerant tef (*Eragrostis tef*) genotypes. *International Research Journal of Plant Science*: 2141-5447, 13(3).
21. **Kebede W.**, Tolosa K., Fikre T., Genet Y., Chanyalew S., Demissie M., Assefa K., Jifar H., Belay N., Bekana G., Gebremeskel K., Chemedo C., Assefa M, Tariku S., Tadele Z. (2022). Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) Variety Development for High Potential Areas of Ethiopia. *American Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*:10(2): 23-28. [DIO:http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.bio.20221002.11](http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.bio.20221002.11)
20. Tolosa T., Edema R., Lamo J., Tilahun N., Abebe D. and **Kebede W.** (2022). Estimating Genotype by Environment Interaction among diverse rice genotypes

identified under artificial conditions. *Journal of Innovative Agriculture*: 9 (1): 17-32. [DIO:http://dx.doi.org/10.37446/jinagri/rsa/9.1.2022.17-32](http://dx.doi.org/10.37446/jinagri/rsa/9.1.2022.17-32)

19. Bekele A., Chanyalew S., Damte T., Husien N., **Kebede W.**, Tolosa K., Genet Y., Assefa K., Nigussie D., Klauser D. and Tadele Z. (2022). Seed-Business Oriented Demonstration Trials: An Efficient Option to Promote Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) Varieties. *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Science*: 32(1) 125-138. [DIO:http://dx.doi.org/10.48350/167394](http://dx.doi.org/10.48350/167394)
18. **Kebede W.**, Tesso B. (2021). Principal Component Analysis of Early Generation Drought Tolerant Tef Genotypes for Yield-contributing Traits. *International Journal of Science, Technology and Society*: Vol. 9, No. 3, 2021, pp. 113-118. [DIO: http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.ijsts.20211003.11](http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.ijsts.20211003.11)
17. **Kebede W.**, Fikre T., Genet Y., Tolosa K., and Chanyalew S. et.al. (2021) “Evaluating the Performance of Tef Genotypes for Improving Yield on high potential areas”, *Journal of Agricultural Research Pesticides and Biofertilizers*: 1(1). [DOI: http://doi.org/05.2021/1.1002](http://doi.org/05.2021/1.1002).
16. **Kebede W.** (2021). Quality traits: measurement and possible breeding method to improve the quality traits of tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter]. *International Journal of Novel Research in Life Sciences*: Vol. 8, Issue 2, pp: (29-40)
15. **Kebede W.** (2021). Cluster and Principal Component Analysis of Drought Tolerant Tef [(Zucc.) Genotypes. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Food Research*: 12: 281
14. **Kebede W** and Assefa K. (2021). Cluster analysis of drought-tolerant tef genotypes. *Journal of Agricultural Research Advance*: 03(01): 12-20.
13. Afeta T., Tesso B., LuleD. and **Kebede W.** (2020). Genetic variability studies among released Faba Bean (*Vicia faba* L.) varieties in central and southern highlands of Ethiopia. *Journal of Agricultural Research Advance*: 02(03): 18-24.
12. Fikre T., Genet Y., **Kebede W.**, Tolossa K., Chanyalew S. et.al. (2020). Yield and Agronomic Performance of Selected Semi-dwarf Tef (*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter) Genotype under Irrigation Farming System in Ethiopia: *American Journal of Plant Biology*: 5(4): 112-121. [DIO: https://doi.org/10.11648/J.AJPB.20200504.16](https://doi.org/10.11648/J.AJPB.20200504.16)
11. **Kebede W.**, Genet Y., Fikre T, Tolosa K., Chanyalew S., Demissie M., Assefa K., G/Meskel K., Fantahun A. and Tadele Z. (2020). Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) variety development for moisture stress areas of Ethiopia: *Journal of Innovative Agriculture*: 7(4): 1-6. [DOI: https://doi.org/10.37446/jinagri/rsa/7.4.2020.1-6](https://doi.org/10.37446/jinagri/rsa/7.4.2020.1-6)
8. Genet Y., Fikre T., **Kebede W.**, Chanyalew S., Tolosa K., Assefa K. (2020). Performance of Selected Tef Genotype for High Potential Areas of Ethiopia. *Ecology and Evolutionary Biology*: Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 35-42. [DIO: http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.eeb.20200503.11](http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.eeb.20200503.11)
7. Genet Y., Fikre T., Assefa K., Chanyalew S., **Kebede W.**, Tolossa K., Jifar H. and Assefaw M. (2020). Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) Recombinant Inbred Line Variety

Development for High Potential Areas of Ethiopia. *Plant*. Vol. 8, No. 4, pp. 93-99.
[DIO: http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.plant.20200804.12](http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.plant.20200804.12)

6. Fikre T., Genet Y., **Kebede W.**, Tolossa K., Assefa K., Chanyalew S., Hussein N., Fentahun A., Belay N. and Tadele Z. (2020). Tef (*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter) Variety 'Felagot'. *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Science*30 (4) 29-37. [DIO: https://boris.unibe.ch/id/eprint/148244](https://boris.unibe.ch/id/eprint/148244)
5. **Kebede W.**, Assefa K., Tesso B., Asfaw M. (2019). Study of broad-sense heritability and genetic advance for grain yield and yield components of drought-tolerant tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] genotypes. *Crop Research Journal*:0970-4884. [DIO: http://dx.doi.org/10.31830/2454-1761.2019.016](http://dx.doi.org/10.31830/2454-1761.2019.016)
4. Chanyalew S., Ferede S., Damte T., Fikre T., Genet Y., **Kebede W.**, Tolossa K., Tadele Z. Assefa K. (2019). Significance and prospects of an orphan crop tef. *An International Journal of Plant Biology*: 0032-0935. [DIO: https://doi.org/10.1007/s00425-019-03209-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00425-019-03209-z)
3. Cannarozzi. G., Chanyalew. S., Assefa. K., Bekele. A., Blösch. R., Weichert. A., Klausner. D. Plaza-Wüthrich. S., Efeld. K., Joßt. M., Rindisbacher. A., Jifar. H., Johnson- Chadwick. V. Abate. E., Wang. W., Rizqah Kamies. K., Hussien. N., **Kebede W.** et al. (2018). Technology generation to dissemination: lessons learned from the tef improvement project; *Euphytica*: 214:31. [DIO: https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-018-2115-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-018-2115-5)
2. **Kebede W.**, Tolossa. K., Hussien. N., Fikre. T., Genet. Y., Bekele. A., Gebremeskel. K., Fentahun. A., Jifar. H., PlazaWüthrich. s., Blösch. R., Chanyalew. S., Assefa. K. and Tadel. Z. (2018). Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) Variety 'Tesfa'; *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Science*: 28(2) 107-112. [DIO: http://dx.doi.org/10.7892/boris.119211](http://dx.doi.org/10.7892/boris.119211)
1. Chanyalew. S., Assefa. K., Asfaw. M., Genet. Y., Tolossa. K., **Kebede W.**, Fikre. T., Hussien. N., Jifar. H., Fentahun. A., Gebremeskel. K., Chemed. G. and Belete. T. (2017). Tef (*Eragrostis tef*) Variety "Dagim"; *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Science*: 27(2) 131-135. [DIO: https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ejas/article/view/156189](https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ejas/article/view/156189)

3.2. Proceeding

1. Chanyalew S., **Kebede W.**, Girma D., Tadele Z. and Assefa K. (eds.) (2020). Tef Improvement: From Where to Where, Proceedings of the Third International Tef Workshop, 22-24 October 2019, Ethio-Resorts, Bishoftu, Ethiopia. <https://my-agriculture.com/2019/11/04/international-tef-workshop/>
2. Gemechu B., Geleta T., **Kebede W.**, Chaynalew S., Assefa K. and Atilew A. (2021). Tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] Seed Production Manual. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center, National Tef Research Program, Debre Zeit, Ethiopia

3.

3.3. Chapter in Book

1. Tara Wight, Sarah Robinson Worku Kebede Kebebew Assefa, Solomon Chanyalew, Zerihun Tadele and Naomi Nakayama (2022). MORPHOLOGY, DEVELOPMENT AND PHENOTYPIC PLASTICITY IN TEF. *In: Kebebew Assefa, Solomon Chanyalew, Dejene Girma, and Zerihun Tadele (Eds.). 2022. Principles and Practices of Tef Improvement. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) and Agricultural Transformation Institute (ATI), Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.48350/176287>
2. Kebebew Assefa, Solomon Chanyalew, Zerihun Tadele, Habte Jifar, Worku Kebede, Tsion Fikre, Kidist Tolossa and Yazachew Genet. (2022). *In: Kebebew Assefa, Solomon Chanyalew, Dejene Girma, and Zerihun Tadele (Eds.). 2022. Principles and Practices of Tef Improvement. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) and Agricultural Transformation Institute (ATI), Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.48350/176289>

3.4. Manual

1. Chanyalew S., **Kebede W.**, Fikre T., Genet Y., Jifar H., Demissie M., Tolossa K., Tadesse M., Tadele Z. and Assefa K. (2021). Tef [*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter] Breeding Manual. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center, National Tef Research Program, Debre Zeit, Ethiopia.
http://www.researchgate.net/publication/359797264_Tef_Breeding_Manual

4. Fellowships

- 2021 Research fellowship on assessing varietal variation in grain morphology in Ethiopian tef (*Eragrostis tef*) germplasm at ILRI in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. <https://www.ilri.org>. for three consecutive months. Major finding was assessing the variation in grain morphology of Ethiopian tef germplasm. About 720 Ethiopian tef germplasms sample measured by using the marvin grain analyzer.

5. Training

- 26 February 2021 Market-Led Breeding Training Jointly organized by EBTI, EARCS and Haramaya University Bishoftu Ethiopia.

23 February 2020	Capacity Building for Food Processing Technology in Ethiopia: Korea Overseas Development and Consulting (KODAC) Soul, Republic of Korea.
22 November 2019	Speed Breeding for Accelerated Crop Improvement in East Africa: KALRO, Field Crop Research Centre, Njoro, Kenya.
24 October 2019	Tef Improvement: From Where to Were, Proceedings of the Third International Tef Workshop Ethio-Resorts, Bishoftu, Ethiopia
28 October 2016	Regional (AFRA) Training Course on Basic Mutation Breeding Techniques for Crop Improvement, Morogoro, United Republic of Tanzania.
23 October 2015	Breeding Management system of Integrated Breeding Platform (IBP); ICRISAT Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural research Bishoftu, Ethiopia
12 June 2015	Basic Research Methodology and statistical computing techniques using R-software; Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural research Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
21 May 2014	Field experimentation, data collection and analysis; Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural research Kulumsa, Ethiopia.

6. Output

6.1. Research Activities

2022	Tef varieties released for commercial uses (white seeded type and brown seeded type) for high potential areas of Ethiopia.
2021	Tef variety released for commercial use BONI (white seeded type and relatively drought-tolerant) for drought-prone areas of Ethiopia.
2020	Tef variety released for commercial use BISHOFTU (white seeded type) for high potential areas of Ethiopia. http://dx.doi.org/10.11648/j.eeb.20200503.11
2019	Tef varieties released for commercial uses (white seeded types) BORA and EBBA for moisture stress and high potential areas, respectively.
2017	Tef varieties released for commercial use TESFA, NIGUS and

FILAGOT (white seeded and brown seeded type) for high potential areas of Ethiopia.

2015 Tef variety released for commercial use DAGIM (white seeded type) for high potential areas of Ethiopia.

7. Research project

2019 - 2021 Principal Investigator (PI) for Ethiopian Government Funded Integrated Tef Project
 2019 – 2022 Boosting Tef Production and Productivities for Improved Livelihood through Generation and Promotion of Appropriate Technology and Information. <https://www.tef-research.org/>

8. Workshops and Conferences

2020 Third International Tef Workshop an organizer of committees.
 2016 Ethiopian Crop Science Society Member

9. Award

2013 Certificate of federal ethics and anti-corruption commission: Adama Science and Technology University
 2013 Certificate of Academic excellence: Adama Science and Technology University

10. Language

Mother tongue(s) Afaan Oromo

Other Languages	Understanding		Speaking		Writing
	Listening	Reading	Spoken interaction	Spoken production	
Amharic	C2	C2	C2	C2	C2
English	C2	C2	C2	C2	C2

Levels: A1 and A2: Basic user - B1 and B2: Independent user - C1 and C2: Proficient user

11. References

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The information I have provided is true and correct.

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